

CHANGES IN PHYSICAL, MECHANICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF LOW WATER DEMANDING CEMENT STRENGTH OVER TIME

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Abstract. One of the most important tasks of the cement production industry is to produce high-quality, low-cost binders using local raw materials widely, to improve the quality of the development of the production of various materials, products and structures based on them, and to reduce the cost of construction, while at the same time stable production and It is important to increase the technical and economic indicators of the production of ecologically clean, local raw materials, effective materials from secondary waste, to improve the durability of the produced materials, and to be used in the construction industry in the territory of the republic. Mechanical activation of cement clinker, addition of finely ground active mineral additives, increase of binder softness and use of superplasticizers allow to save cement at a high level. The factors related to the creation of new generations of cement, the use of innovative technologies, the reduction of high-quality raw material resources, the increase of industrial waste and the increase of environmental problems are the main reasons. This is important in evaluating the effectiveness of the use of various mineral additives in cement and concrete products to solve such problems. It is urgent to develop low water requiring cements based on active mineral additives such as endless desert sands, and wastes like Angren ash from thermal power plant, microsilica from the Bekobod metallurgical plant available in the territories of Uzbekistan, to select their optimal composition, and to study their main properties.

Keywords: low water demand cement, desert sand, microsilica, fly ash, superplasticizer.

Introduction. A low-water demanding binder is a low-consumption, high-activity hydraulic binder that is active mineral compound together with cement or clinker, active mineral additives, gypsum, or superplasticizers in powder form to reduce water content. The water requirement of a low water demanding binder varies to 10-15% compared to ordinary cement. By using local raw materials and industrial wastes wisely, it is possible to obtain less water-demanding binders, which can significantly reduce the amount of cement used in the production of building materials and structures, [1]. It has been suggested that in low water-to-cement ratio (w/c) concretes, the “coarser” cement particles could be replaced by an “inert” filler with little loss in performance in terms of hydration and strength development, [2]. For low w/c ratio concrete, a large proportion (more than 35%) of portland cement remains unhydrated acting as an expensive and energy-consuming filler. The use of lime stone filler in this mixture is a more rational option from the energy consumption, emission reduction, and economic point of view. The optimum level of limestone addition depends on the concrete mixture proportions, [3]. As cement hydration proceeds in low water-to-cement ratio (w/c) cement paste, the water becomes bound into hydration products and adsorbed on their surfaces. Since hydration products have smaller volume than the reactants, the total volume of a cement paste decreases during hydration,[4]. It turned out that the strength of the binder of low water demand (BLWD) is approximately two times higher than the strength of the initial cement, and dilute BLW with 50 to 70% of the ground slag or quartz sand in their composition provided the same strength as the original Portland cement. Approximately 70 to 80% of the total contribution to the

increase in strength was achieved due to a reduction in the water requirement of the mixture and the preparation of cement stone and mortar at sufficiently low values of the water-cement ratio and, accordingly, an increase in their density, and 20-30% due to an increase in the fineness of the grind and the specific surface of the cement And the creation of a more solid and monolithic fine-grained structure of the material, [5]. It is shown that the cement of low water demand, in which the advantages of both Portland cement and mineral additives are more fully and efficiently presented, complies with the tendency to decrease the clinker volume to the greatest degree. It is established that the clinker volume index for heavy concrete prepared on low water demand cement is almost four times lower than that for heavy concrete based on common Portland cement, [6]. On the other way, SP is also the barrier of wide LWDC' utilization because of its high cost – it takes part in binder's mass up to 3%. Basically it is closely connected with fact that dry SP is produced from its water-based solution and desiccation process increases cost of admixture from 2 to 4 times, [7]. The most productive and widely used approach, which does not require reconstruction of cement plants, is to reduce the clinker capacity in cement during the grinding of clinker with substitutional hydraulic, pozzolanic, “inert”) additives. Nevertheless, such a dilution affects the performance of cement and reduces the' strength, especially when using limestone – the most available cement filler; carbon dioxide emissions per standard cement strength are not reduced, [8]. The addition of SP increased the packing density and the water film thickness of pastes with a w/b of 0.32 and 0.24. However, the increase of SP dosage had little effect on the packing density and the water film thickness of pastes with a very low w/b (0.16). For the cement pastes

with a very low w/b (e.g., 0.16), the small spaces between the binder particles and the high concentration of the un-adsorbed SP in the interstitial solution may be the primary factors responsible for the increase in viscosity of the pastes, [9]. They are able to contain up to 90% of waste without loss of quality properties. The technology is safe for the environment, less energy-intensive, and technologically simple. Since the introduction of CLWD production allows to significantly reduce carbon dioxide emissions (by 3-4 times), this technology can be attributed to the so-called “green technologies.” A low indicator of the clinker capacity of these binders determines it as a resource-saving technology, [10]. Using an LWDC technology makes it possible to decrease significantly CO₂ emission (up to 3-4 times), and utilize up to 70% of wastes such as fly ash per 1 ton of binder, also it could be built in “classic” technology of OPC without colossal investments and readjustments. LWDC technology could be rightfully assigned as one of the best available technologies for mineral binders’ production, [11]. Low water demanding cement (LWDC) absorbs a certain amount of water to form a normal density, which gives it a certain consistency. In the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan, the introduction of microsilica increases the water demand of LWDC, which even reaches 30%, but the water demand can be reduced to 20% by adding a superplasticizer from 0.6 to 0.8%. microsilica, due to its high dispersion, absorbs more water than the original cement, [1]. Reduction of water demand of cement pastes results in the decrease of cement matrix porosity and, accordingly, in the increase of its strength and durability. Reducing the water demand of pastes based on low-clinker binders while ensuring their high fluidity is considered one of the main problems in the production of cement composites of high strength and durability. The solution to this problem can be attained by using superplasticizers (SPs) as well as multicomponent SCMs which can enhance the effect of superplasticizers, [12]. A significant factor limiting the use of this positive effects is the fact that by the decrease of the w/c ratios, the workability of the fresh composite mixture and the resulting engineering properties of the hardened composite are decreased. A limited solution enables the use of the plasticizers or of the superplasticizers. A very attractive solution represents the combination of super low w/c ratios, under w/c 0.1 and deeper, resulting in a submicroscopic pore structure and an adequate high quality of the engineering properties of the composite, [13].

Main part. The production of high-performance cements from a chemical point of view, the effective use of their components, the type and amount of components used in their composition, is carried out along with obtaining high-quality concretes designed for various functional purposes with completely new properties and a predetermined structure. The principle of appropriate control at all stages of technologies for creating such cements includes: the use of active components, the development of optimal compositions,

the use of chemical modifiers, the use of mechanical-chemical activation of components and other methods. LWDC cement production is also based on this principle.

The structure and properties of LWDC are predetermined by the selection of the necessary starting materials, as well as their ratio, degree of softness and activity. The degree of softness of cement can play a negative role in certain conditions, so we believe that it is necessary to consider the degree of softness of cement every time.

Hydration processes of LWDC develop differently depending on the type of components that make up the cement in the hardening system. In the hydration processes that take place in the hardening system, it is necessary to take into account the type, activity and other factors of the superplasticizer and the used mineral additive, as well as clinker active minerals for hydration.

Syngenite, portlandite and gypsum do not adsorb superplasticizers. Consequently, superplasticizers adsorbed to the hydrating cement grain accumulate mainly in spots where ettringite crystallizes. As a result, the uneven distribution of polymer molecules on its surface creates a mosaic structure for hydrated cement grains. The absolute values of the zeta potential for an ettringite or other mineral phase depend on the concentration of potentially determining ions present in the pore solution. Although they may differ in cement composition, S/Ts, hydration time, etc., the same relative order of zeta potential values can be expected for different hydration phases and minerals present. Measuring the zeta potential of any cementitious material (eg, limestone, fly ash, etc.) allows a rapid determination of its adsorbent potential. Such results, together with data on the specific surface area, provide a rough estimate of the superplasticizer dosage required to disperse a given system. It also provides insight into cement-superplasticizer interactions.

Figure 3.5.1. (Microsilica and Barkhan) IR spectrum of LWDC-55 powder

In the IR spectrum of LWDC-55 (microsilica and barkhan) sample (Fig. 3.5.1), the main bands can be divided into 3 sections. The first most intense bands are located in the area of 800-1100 cm⁻¹. These correspond to the valence vibration of the SO₄ group of gypsum at 1106 cm⁻¹. And the band at 920 cm⁻¹ corresponds to

asymmetric vibrations of SiO_4 . The peak near this band at 874 cm^{-1} corresponds to the in-plane deformational vibration of the carbonate group formed as the cement carbonates. The second group of bands can be expressed as follows. In the spectrum of this sample, the frequency at 795 cm^{-1} originates from the valence vibrations of the tetrahedral group of AlO_4 in S_3A . The lowest band at 665 cm^{-1} of the spectrum corresponds to the deformation vibration of SiO_4 . The third bands are the high frequency part of the spectrum. This can be seen from the very weak signal at 3391 cm^{-1} , which indicates that the gray powder sample contains very little calcium hydroxide.

Figure 3.5.1. IR spectrum of LWDC-55 (microsilica and ash) powder

In the IR spectrum (Fig. 3.5.2) of the LWDC-55 (microsilica and ash) sample, the main bands are also similar to those of the above sample. These correspond to the valence vibration of the SO_4 group of gypsum at 1110 cm^{-1} . And the band at 918 cm^{-1} corresponds to asymmetric vibrations of SiO_4 . The peak near this band at 874 cm^{-1} corresponds to the in-plane deformational vibration of the carbonate group formed as the cement carbonates. In the spectrum of this sample, the frequency at 798 cm^{-1} originates from the valence vibrations of the tetrahedral group of AlO_4 in S_3A . The lowest band of the spectrum at 669 cm^{-1} corresponds to the deformation vibration of SiO_4 . It can also be seen from the very weak signal at 3395 cm^{-1} that the black powder sample contains very little calcium hydroxide.

Figure 3.5.3. IR spectrum of LWDC-55 hardened for 28 days (microsilica and barkhan).

In the IR spectrum of the cement sample hardened

for 28 days (microsilica and barkhan), there are significant changes in the medium and high frequency range. This can be seen in the appearance of bands of valence vibrations at 3619 , 3747 and 3843 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the OH groups of calcium hydroxide, calcium silicate hydrate and hydrogen-bonded water. The following bands at 2983 cm^{-1} and adjacent bands at frequencies of 1510 and 1409 cm^{-1} can be considered as signals of overtone vibrations of tricalcium silicate - C_3S bands. The band at 2278 cm^{-1} originates from the valence vibrations of the O-C-O group. The deformation vibration of the OH group of hydrated calcium silicate appears at 1693 cm^{-1} . The bands at 1510 and 1409 cm^{-1} originate from hydrated C_3S . A band corresponding to the valence vibrations of the tetrahedral SiO_4 group appeared at 956 cm^{-1} . The weak band at 874 cm^{-1} is due to the deformation vibration of the C-O bond. Also, in the lowest part of the spectrum, the deformation vibration corresponding to SiO_4 is visible at 668 cm^{-1} .

Figure 3.5.4. IR spectrum of LWDC-55 hardened for 28 days (microsilica and ash).

In the IR spectrum of the cement sample hardened for 28 days (microsilica and ash), there are significant changes in the medium and high frequency range. This can be seen especially in the appearance of valence vibration bands at 3616 , 3744 and 3847 cm^{-1} corresponding to the OH groups of calcium hydroxide, calcium silicate hydrate and hydrogen-bonded water. The following bands at 2988 cm^{-1} and 2908 cm^{-1} can be evaluated as signals of overtone vibrations of tricalcium silicate - C_3S bands at frequencies of 1518 and 1415 cm^{-1} . The band at 2268 cm^{-1} originates from the valence vibrations of the O-C-O group. The strain vibration of the OH group of hydrated calcium silicate appears at 1695 cm^{-1} . The bands at 1518 and 1415 cm^{-1} originate from hydrated C_3S . A band corresponding to the valence vibrations of the tetrahedral SiO_4 group appeared at 958 cm^{-1} . And the weak band at 867 cm^{-1} originates from the deformation vibration of the C-O bond. Also, in the lowest part of the spectrum, the deformation vibration corresponding to SiO_4 is visible at 671 cm^{-1} .

Electron microscopic analysis. Figure 3.5.5 presents an image of LWDC-55 (B'-microsilica and barkhan) cement powder taken under a scanning electron microscope. In an electron microscope, it is also

possible to see the distribution of different phases when microanalyzing element cards. It was found that the main phase consists of tricalcium silicate (allite) - $3\text{CaO}\cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$, followed by belite - Ca_2SiO_4 , three-calcium aluminate - $3\text{CaO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, four-calcium aluminoferrite - $4\text{CaO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, and potash -

K_2SO_3 . This sample also contains a small amount of gypsum - $\text{CaSO}_4\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and periclase - MgO .

In the LWDC-55 (B- microsilica and ash) cement sample, its color is darker due to the relatively large amount of ferrite.

Figure 3.5.5. Electron microscope view of LWDC-55 (A-microsilica and ash, A'-microsilica and barkhan) powder.

The following can be seen from the electron micrographs of hardened cement samples. In this case, three-calcium silicate and two-calcium silicate, three-calcium aluminate, and calcium hydroxide are also formed under the influence of moisture, and a sharp change in structure is observed. This is also explained by the increase in the percentage of calcium in the form of powder from 21% to 32%. This process can be explained by the following reaction equation: $\text{CaO}_{(q)} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(s)} \rightarrow \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_{2(q)}$

Figure 3.5.6. Electron microscope appearance of LWDC-55 (S,B,G- microsilica and ash, C',B',G'-microsilica and barkhan) stones hardened in 28 days.

In the morphology of cement powder, the following can be distinguished: the gel-like material surrounding the cement grains. In hardened cement samples, the main hydration products are amorphous, fibrous and granular. The C-S-H phase consists of an irregular core with characteristic peripheral fibrous growth. A high density of typical hexagonal plates of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ can be observed inside the capillary pores. Most of the large pores are completely or partially filled with hydration products and condensed (Fig. 3.5.6).

The magnesium oxide-periclas phase in cement

does not change significantly before and after hydration. Also, potash in ash and silicates in sand do not change due to their low reactivity and appear as a very small black background in the electron micrograph.

Powder X-ray diffraction is widely used to determine the phase composition of cement samples. In order to determine the phases in it, the interplanar distance of the crystalline substances that can be found in the cement and the diffraction angles satisfying the Breg condition due to structural interference were compared.

It is known that the main part of cement is alite - C_3S ,

belite - C_2S , aluminate - C_3A and aluminoferrite - S_4AF . Each of them has a crystalline structure, and the final X-ray diffraction pattern of the sample corresponds to their properties. But since it has a complex structure, the quantitative analysis of cement content is quite problematic. It is especially difficult to separate the phases when the peaks in the diffraction angle between $20 - 35^\circ$ overlap.

The following table shows the distance between diffraction planes of LWDC-55 (microsilica and barkhan) powder:

Table 3.1. LWDC-55 powder diffractogram interplanar distance

№	2θ	θ	d-distance
1	16,36053	8,180265	0,813205
2	21,00827	10,50414	0,8737
3	27,11811	13,55906	0,919766
4	29,82475	14,91238	1,078436
5	36,94442	18,47221	2,09062
6	39,86059	19,9303	0,873053
7	40,6569	20,32845	0,773564
8	42,55817	21,27909	1,178915
9	46,26996	23,13498	0,84627
10	50,59165	25,29583	4,744342
12	60,40443	30,20222	0,82216
13	63,56954	31,78477	2,136536
15	68,64413	34,32207	3,301974

Figure 3.5.7. X-ray image of LWDC-55 (microsilica and barkhan) powder.

The peaks at 27.06° , 42.87° and 50.73° in the diffractogram of KSTTs-55 (microsilica and barkhan) cement powder sample (Figure 3.5.7) were determined to belong to tricalcium silicate. The peaks at 21.09° and 37.0° can be estimated to belong to tricalcium aluminate. The peak corresponding to magnesium oxide-periclase almost coincides with the peak at 42.87° and is located to the right of it.

Figure 3.5.8. X-ray image of LWDC-55 (microsilica and ash) powder.

From the above diffractogram (Figure 3.5.8) LWDC-55, (microsilica and fly ash) cement powder, the peaks at 27.07° , 42.59° , 50.5° and 68.69° belong to tricalcium silicate, and the peaks at 16.2° and 29.84° belong to gypsum, the peaks at 21.02° and 36.98° can be estimated as belonging to tricalcium aluminate. The peak corresponding to magnesium oxide-periclase appears at 42.59° .

Figure 3.5.9. X-ray image of LWDC-55 (microsilica and barkhan) cement stone hardened in 28 days.

New peaks appear at 18.08° , 34.21° and 47.16° in the diffractogram of KSTTs-55 (microsilica and ash) cement hardened for 28 days (Fig. 3.5.9). This can be explained by the formation of calcium hydroxide when free calcium oxide reacts with water. That is, the calcium oxide in the tricalcium silicate, which is the main component of cement, reacts with water and causes the formation of new phases. The absence of peaks at 27.06° and 68.54° for tricalcium silicate in Figure 3.5.7 in the 28-day hardened cement sample indicates that the hydration products have an amorphous structure.

In the diffractogram of the black cement sample hardened for 28 days (Fig. 3.5.10), due to the presence of Barkhan sand, the peak corresponding to tricalcium silicate is clearly distinguished at 26.76° . In addition, due to the formation of calcium hydroxide as above, the peak corresponding to calcium hydroxide at 18.08° dominates. All three cement samples have a peak at

16.01°, which can be explained by the fact that gypsum does not change its structure during hydration.

Figure 3.5.10. X-ray image of LWDC-55 (microsilica and ash) stone, which has hardened in 28 days.

The obtained samples were examined in the NEX DE energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer of the Rikagu firm (Table 3.2, 3.3). The components of the powder samples were compared with the samples solidified for 28 days. The mass changes of the components were studied in oxide form. It can be seen that the mass of CaO is slightly higher in the hardened cement sample. This can be explained by the formation of additional structures under the influence of moisture.

Table 3.3. Composition of powder and hardened LWDC-55 (microsilica and barkhan) cement samples (mass %)

No	KSTTs-55 (microsilica and barkhan) components of cement (in the oxide state)	Powder sample (mass %)	28-day hardened sample (mass %)
1	SiO ₂	38,5	17,6
2	CaO	48,8	70,1
3	Fe ₂ O ₃	4,41	3,81
4	Al ₂ O ₃	5,89	5,31
5	SO ₃	4,71	3,23

Based on the data in the table, it can be seen that the mass of CaO is much higher in the hardened cement sample. Due to the large amount of CaO in the sample in powder form, calcium hydroxide was also formed under the influence of water, and a high increase in its mass was observed.

The conclusions based on the results of electronic analysis are as follows: the lines related to the functional groups in C3S, C2S, C3A, C4AF were analyzed in the powdered cement samples, the intensity of the lines related to the hydroxyl group in the new products formed from the reaction in the solidified cement samples was found to increase sharply, the main content of the solidified cement. It was confirmed that the phase - that is, the reaction product is the calcium hydroxide phase, the diffractogram of the newly formed calcium hydroxide phase in the solidified cement showed that

the carbonate phase is partially formed due to the carbon dioxide in the air, the elemental analysis of the samples corresponds quantitatively to the IR and X-ray diffraction analyses. It is confirmed that the content is suitable for the intended purpose.

Conclusions. 1. The effect of the amount of active mineral additives in LWDCement on the mechanical properties of the resulting cement stone was determined.

2. The optimal parameters of LWDCcements with a specific surface area of 5500-6000 cm²/g were determined technologically and economically.

3. Based on the results of the analysis of the strength diagrams for the optimization of LWDCement composition, it was determined that the factors that significantly affect the strength of cement are the amount of silica-containing microsilica, residual ash, barkhan sand.

4. It was determined that one of the main factors in the preparation of LWDCcement using microsilica, residual ash, barkhan sand is the ability of silicon dioxide to interact with calcium hydroxide in the hardening cement stone.

5. The composition, activity, costs of LWDCements are scientifically and economically based.

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